

Development of suitability maps for solar power solutions

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Abstract

This study assesses suitability for establishing solar power solutions in three case studies in Europe: Gotland in Sweden, Tarn-et-Garonne in France, and Southern Great Plain in Hungary. For each case study, suitability maps are produced, representing: 1) Photovoltaic plants; 2) Agrovoltatics; 3) Floating solar photovoltaic panels in water bodies; 4) Spatial planning for the sustainable deployment of solar energy on land; 5) Land management of solar photovoltaic systems land. The suitability maps are created as part of the RethinkAction Horizon 2020 project, which is developing an interdisciplinary platform for decision-making, centred on land-use based adaptation and mitigation solutions for climate change.

The results from each case study are compared to address the following research questions: 1) How and why does the suitability for solar power development vary among the case studies? and 2) What are the possibilities and limitations of the developed methodology in assessing the suitability for solar power solutions in the diverse geographic and environmental conditions of the case studies?

The results show the most potential area for photovoltaic plants and agrovoltatics in Southern Great Plain in Hungary, followed by Tarn-et-Garonne and lastly Gotland. The amount of protected areas and the type of land use have a large impact on the difference, where Gotland has more protected areas and less areas with land use suitable for solar power installation. If stricter suitability classification is enforced where arable land is not deemed suitable for solar power installation, Gotland instead has the highest percentual part suitable area.

The developed method is created to fit a variety of areas with diverse characteristic and uses data that are free to use for research purposes. It can therefore be replicated in future studies with different land characteristics, though the general applicability comes with limitations of precision. In the RethinkAction project, these suitability maps will serve as inputs for further analysis, together with other land-use based adaptation and mitigation solutions.

Keywords

Solar power solutions, Suitability maps, GIS, Land Use, Photovoltaic

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Table of acronyms

Table 1. The acronyms used in this paper.

Abbreviation	Explanation
CS	Case Study
DEM	Digital Elevation Model
FPV	Floating Photovoltaics
GTI	Global Tilted Irradiance
HR LU L2	High Resolution Land Use Level 2
LAMS	Land-use Adaptation and Mitigation Solution
NMD	National Land Cover Database
OSM	OpenStreetMap
PAWC	Plant Available Water Content
PV	Photovoltaic
SDG	Sustainable Development Goals

1 Introduction

Solar power technology plays an important role in meeting the rising global energy demand while phasing out non-renewable energy (Pastuszek & Węgierek, 2022). An increase of solar energy as a renewable energy source is important for several of the United Nations Sustainable Development Goals (SDG). Renewable energy is mentioned explicitly in SDG 7 (*Ensure access to affordable, reliable, sustainable and modern energy for all*), but it also contributes to e.g. SDG 9 (*Build resilient infrastructure, promote inclusive and sustainable industrialization and foster innovation*), SDG 12 (*Ensure sustainable consumption and production patterns*), and SDG 13 (*Take urgent action to combat climate change and its impacts*) (United Nations, 2015). The most used technology for transforming solar irradiation to electrical energy is photovoltaic (PV). The global installation of PV panels has grown rapidly in the last decade from 176 GW installed capacity in 2014 to 1412 GW in 2023 (IRENA, 2024). In 2022 solar energy produced 1310 TWh electricity globally, which accounted for 4.6% of total electricity production (Ember & Our World in Data, 2023).

One way of planning for spatial allocation of solar power is using GIS software to create suitability maps (Günen, 2021). Factors that are regarded as important for the specific solar power solution, are combined to create maps that visualise how suitable different parts of an area are for the solution (ibid.).

This degree project produces suitability maps for solar power solutions in Europe, on behalf of IVL Swedish Environmental Research Institute, to be used in the RethinkAction Horizon 2020 project.

1.1 The RethinkAction project and Land-use based adaptation and mitigation solutions (LAMS)

RethinkAction is a project developing an interdisciplinary platform for decision-making, centred on land-use based adaptation and mitigation solutions (LAMS) for climate change. It is funded by European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme. The partners involved in RethinkAction are CARTIF, University of Valladolid, IVL Swedish Environmental Research Institute, RINA, CMCC, Climate Media Factory, National Observatory of Athens, GMW, FCIências.ID, ICLEI, Institute for Environment and Human Security, Geonardo, and INRAE. The project started in October 2021 and will be finished in September 2025. It focuses on six European case studies, which were chosen to represent the regional differences of Europe related to effects of the changing climate. The case studies are 1) Gotland, Sweden's largest island located in the Baltic Sea; 2) Tarn-et-Garonne, a French district located in between the Atlantic Ocean and Mediterranean Sea; 3) Southern Great Plain, a Hungarian region dominated by agricultural land; 4) Valle D'Aosta, an alpine area in north-western Italy; 5) Almería, a Spanish region bordering the Mediterranean Sea; and 6) Azores Archipelago, a group of smaller islands located 1450 km from mainland Portugal in the Atlantic Ocean (RethinkAction n.d.).

The results of this master thesis are part of the RethinkAction work package 6.2. In 6.2 suitability maps are produced for LAMS in the areas Agriculture, Biodiversity and ecosystems, Energy, Forestry, Urban, and Water management. A total of thirteen suitability maps are produced for each of the case study areas. This master thesis presents the method and results for five of the suitability maps, in the Energy category, for three

of the case studies, Gotland, Tarn-et-Garonne and Southern Great Plain. The suitability maps produced in this master thesis corresponds to the RethinkAction LAMS 1) Photovoltaic plans, 2) Agrovoltaics, 3) Floating solar photovoltaic panels in water bodies, 4) Spatial planning for the sustainable deployment of solar energy on land, and 5) Land management of solar photovoltaic systems land. These five LAMS are explained in more detail below.

1.1.1 Photovoltaic plants

This LAMS investigates the potential for PV plants, which is a power plant consisting of arrays of PV panels, each built up by several cells that generate electricity from solar irradiation (Cabrera-Tobar et al. 2016). The EU commission (2022) views PV energy as one of the most competitive sources of energy within the region and describes that PV energy has a key role in the transition towards clean energy and breaking the reliance on fossil fuel. As part of the REPowerEU plan, goals are set to reach 320 GW solar photovoltaic capacity by 2025 and 600 GW by 2030 (European commission, 2022), compared to 255 GW in 2023 (IRENA, 2024).

1.1.2 Agrovoltaics

Agrovoltaics, the combination of agriculture and PV panels on the same land, was suggested already in 1982 as a way of avoiding the land-use conflicts associated with building PV panels on land that is used or could be used for agriculture (Goetzberger & Zastrow, 1982). According to Weselek et al. (2019), PV panels affect the microclimate of the underlying fields, which can have a negative or positive effect on the crop yield depending on crop type, degree of shading and climatological factors of the site. These effects are associated with the direct solar irradiation, decreased evapotranspiration and differences in temperature. To minimize negative effect on the agriculture, the PV panels are installed at least 4-5m above ground on stands with enough room between pillars for agricultural machinery to move around underneath. The photovoltaic cells are installed more sparsely than in normal photovoltaic installation to reduce negative effects associated with shadowing (Weselek et al., 2019). Agrovoltaics is not only a way of avoiding a land use conflict but can also increase income for farmers as the land generates income from both agriculture and energy production (Dinesh & Pearce, 2016).

1.1.3 Floating solar photovoltaic panels in water bodies

Another way of avoiding conflicting land use is by placing the PV panels on floating pontoons in waterbodies such as lakes, ponds, and dams (Sahu, Yadav & Sudhakar, 2016). Floating photovoltaics (FPV) offers several other benefits compared to land-based PV. FPV have higher efficiency than land-based PV as the water cools the PV cells, and the cells generates more power in lower temperatures (Cazzaniga et al., 2018). FPV can help reduce algae growth and evapotranspiration as they limit the sunlight reaching the water surface, however too high surface coverage might have negative effects on the aquatic ecosystem (Haas et al., 2020).

1.1.4 Spatial planning for the sustainable deployment of solar energy on land

For widespread deployment of solar energy, it is important not only to include technical, geographical, and economic aspects but also environmental, social, cultural, and political (Spyridonidou et al., 2022). The LAMS Spatial planning for the sustainable deployment of solar energy on land is similar to the LAMS Photovoltaic plants but includes stricter rules of which areas that are classified as suitable. Areas with proximity to religious, touristic, archaeological, and historical sites are not considered suitable, the distance from coast is increased and a stricter view of which land use types are considered suitable is implemented.

1.1.5 Land management of solar photovoltaic systems land

The land use change associated with building a photovoltaic plant can lead to negative effects on biodiversity and a carbon release (Armstrong, Ostle & Whitaker, 2015). To compensate for these negative effects different types of land management practices can be applied to the area (Van de Ven et al., 2021). Through land management such as seeding the ground to use it as pastures (ibid.), planting native grass and herbs, or providing habitats for pollinators, positive effects can be created for both ecosystems and for humans (Hernandez et al., 2019). This LAMS focuses on current solar land and the potential for land management measures to increase biodiversity or carbon uptake of those areas.

1.2 Aim and research questions

The aim of this study is to create suitability maps for the RethinkAction project that will be used as 1) standalone open products for use by e.g. decision makers when planning for deployment of solar power, and as 2) input data for further analysis in the RethinkAction project. This degree project also serves the purpose of contributing to the development of the methodology used in RethinkAction, which focuses on investigating suitability of solar power solutions in case study areas with diverse geographical and environmental conditions. The developed methodology is evaluated by comparison with previous similar studies, and by exchanging input land use data to compare the differences in output results. The following research questions were chosen:

1. How and why does the suitability for solar power development vary among the case studies?
2. What are the possibilities and limitations of the developed methodology in assessing the suitability for solar power solutions in the diverse geographic and environmental conditions of the case studies?

2 Method

2.1 Case study characteristics

The case studies (CS) of RethinkAction are presented in Table 2 and their location is shown in Figure 1.

Table 2. The six case studies of the RethinkAction project.

Case study	Area name	Country	Description
1	Gotland	Sweden	Northern area case study
2	Tarn-et-Garonne	France	Atlantic case study
3	Southern Great Plain	Hungary	Continental case study
4	Valle d'Aosta	Italy	Alpine case study
5	Almería	Spain	Mediterranean case study
6	Azores Archipelago	Portugal	Small island case study

Figure 1. The location of the six RethinkAction case study areas.

The three case studies of this degree project are Gotland, Tarn-et-Garonne and Southern Great Plain.

CS1 Gotland, situated in the Baltic Sea, is Sweden's largest island. The case study has an area of 3179 km². It has a land cover dominated by forest as seen in Figure 2, where a total of 54% belongs to the land use classes forest managed or forest primary. 29% of the area is rainfed or irrigated cropland. Gotland has no area classified as solar land.

CS2 Tarn-et-Garonne is situated in south-western France, in between the Mediterranean Sea and the Atlantic Ocean. It has an area of 3731 km² and is dominated by cropland, with 71% land use classified as either irrigated or rainfed cropland (Figure 2). It has an area of 66 ha currently classified as solar land, which is 0.018% of the total area.

CS3 Southern great plain is the Hungarian case study in the south-eastern part of the country. It has the largest area of all the case studies, 18 334 km². 80% of the area is covered by either irrigated or rainfed cropland (Figure 2). CS3 has 60 ha solar land, corresponding to 0.003% of the total area.

Figure 2. Land use of each study area according to the dataset High Resolution Land Use Level 2, produced within the RethinkAction project. The exact percentual land use is shown for land use classes with at least 10% coverage.

2.2 General methodology for suitability map production

The method of suitability map production used in this degree project was developed together with other partners in the RethinkAction project. The suitability map production phase took place in between 15/1 and 10/3, 2024, with minor modifications made afterward. Some general guidelines were set to assure that the suitability maps were produced in a similar way and yielded comparable results. These general guidelines were continuously discussed in bi-weekly meetings and updated throughout the map production phase. From these guidelines a workflow was developed for each LAMS, which in some cases had to be further developed to suit different case study conditions. The energy LAMS workflow for CS 1, 2 and 3 developed in this degree project is presented in Figure 3. CARTIF was responsible for the suitability map production of the energy LAMS in CS 4, 5 and 6. To produce compatible suitability maps, CARTIF and I had weekly meetings during the map production phase, where our methods and models were discussed to ensure equivalent results. Since CARTIF worked with different software the methods used do not completely align, but the differences are regarding technical aspects and should not affect the outcome of the suitability maps.

Figure 3. General flowchart for the energy LAMS suitability maps.

2.2.1 Data and suitability factor selection

To produce suitability maps for the LAMS, multiple factors that affect the suitability were combined. These factors were in large parts chosen before the start of this master thesis in an earlier RethinkAction deliverable, by other associates within the project. The deliverable also included suggestions of datasets associated with the suitability factors

and suggested values for what would be regarded as suitable and not suitable for most of the factors (Hellsten et al., 2023). The suggested suitability factors and suitable values of the factors were based on literature review of previous similar studies. The articles that were most used for this were Günen (2021), Noorollahi et al. (2016), Spyridonidou et al. (2022), Elkadeem et al. (2024) and Chawin (2023).

Throughout the work process the preparatory work had to be modified. Some suitability factors were exchanged or excluded, some datasets were not available for download or were not suited for the suitability factors, and suitability classification values had to be modified according to the conditions of the case studies and datasets. These modifications were made in meetings with CARTIF.

2.2.2 Data preparation

The workflow for the creation of the energy LAMS suitability maps can be divided into two sections, data preparation and suitability map production (Figure 3). The data preparation section included finding and downloading the datasets for each suitability factor, reprojecting the data to EPSG:3035, clipping them with polygons representing each study area with a 10 km buffer, and transforming the files to shapefile or GeoTIFF. The 10km buffers around the study areas served as margins to incorporate objects outside the study area that could affect suitability. The resampling technique used in the reprojection was nearest neighbour for categorical data and bilinear for continuous data when resampling from coarser resolution, and majority for categorical and average for numerical when resampling from finer resolution.

As a lot of suitability factors were used in multiple LAMS suitability maps, the data preparation step was done in collaboration with the other suitability map producers in RethinkAction. When data for a suitability factor was prepared, as described above, it was uploaded to a shared cloud storage. My contribution in this step was downloading and preparing data for crop type, power grids, water depth, buildings, and historical, archaeological, religious, and touristic sites for all case studies. I downloaded LiDAR data for CS1 and high-resolution DSM for CS2. I reviewed other colleagues prepared data and I was involved in the discussions regarding how we could minimize distortion when resampling and reprojecting. The data preparation was done in Python 3.12.1 using the packages *geopandas*, *rasterio* and *shapely*.

2.2.3 Suitability map production

Suitability maps were created using the model builder of ArcGIS Pro 3.1.0. The prepared data were processed, as shown in Figure 3, to create a raster file for each suitability factor with 10m cell size, classified by suitability. The workflow can be divided into two main groups depending on the data type and suitability factor: a) raster data with suitability classes directly associated with raster values, and b) raster or vector data where the suitability is determined by distance from objects or pixel values.

For the first group the raster data were first reclassified into suitability classes (Reclassify B in Figure 3). They were then resampled to 10m cell size with nearest neighbour as resampling technique and the land use data as snap raster. The raster data included in the second group were first reclassified to only contain the relevant information for the suitability factor (Reclassify A in Figure 3). For example, when calculating distance from water, all pixels not representing water in a land use dataset were reclassified to NODATA. New raster layers were then created containing distance from the remaining cells in the raster files, as well as to objects in the vector files, with 10m cell size and the land use data as snap raster. These distance raster layers were then reclassified after suitability. When reclassifying after suitability (Reclassify B in Figure 3) the raster layers were either classified on a four-grade scale of not suitable to most suitable, or as just suitable or not suitable. The four-grade scale classified factors were used both to

rank pixels after suitability and to exclude unsuitable areas, while the two-grade scale classified factors were only used to exclude unsuitable areas. The reclassification values are presented in Table 3.

Table 3. The table shows how the reclassification was executed in the step labelled Reclassify (B) in Figure 3.

Factor type	Suitability classes
Factors classified as Most suitable, Moderately suitable, Least suitable and Not suitable	3 – Most suitable 2 – Moderately suitable 1 – Least suitable NODATA – Not suitable
Factors only classified as Suitable and Not suitable	0 - Suitable NODATA – Not suitable

When each suitability factor had an associated raster layer classified after suitability, suitability maps were produced with the raster calculator. An average suitability was calculated to pixels that were deemed suitable in each suitability factor. If a cell was classified as not suitable in any suitability factor it was deemed not suitable for the entire suitability map, and therefore excluded. To do this, each layer was added through addition and then the sum was divided by the number of four-grade classified layers. This way a suitability map was created with a ranking of 1-3 for each suitable pixel, with all unsuitable areas excluded as NODATA. To get a suitability map only displaying integer numbers 0-3, this initial suitability map was reclassified again according to Table 4 (Reclassify C in Figure 3). The case study border was used as both mask and extent to exclude areas outside the study area and to change all NODATA values within the study area to 0.

Table 4. The table shows how the reclassification was executed in the step labelled Reclassify (C) in Figure 3.

Input value	Reclassified value
NODATA	0
$1 \leq x \leq 1.5$	1
$1.5 < x \leq 2.5$	2
$2.5 < x \leq 3$	3

2.3 LAMS-specific suitability map production

The general method described above had to be adapted to fit the different LAMS. A more detailed description of each LAMS suitability map method is provided below.

2.3.1 Photovoltaic plants

The workflow of the LAMS Photovoltaic plants is presented in Figure 4. The input data for this suitability map were a digital elevation model (DEM), Global Tilted Irradiance (GTI), land use as raster layers, as well as vector layers containing rivers, roads, power lines, protected areas and the case study boundary. Slope and aspect were created from the DEM and a raster containing water bodies was created from the land use data. The created raster layers containing distance from waterbodies and rivers were combined with a minimum algorithm to create a layer containing distance from all water sources. For CS1 a distance from the case study boundary was also included in the minimum

calculation as the boundary aligns with the coast. The suitability of each suitability factor was reclassified according to Table 5.

Figure 4. Flowchart for the suitability map of the LAMS Photovoltaic plants.

Table 5. Classification of the suitability factors for the LAMS Photovoltaic plants.

Suitability factor	Most suitable	Moderately suitable	Least Suitable	Not suitable
Land Use	Sparsely vegetated	Rainfed cropland, Grassland, Shrubland, Irrigated cropland	Forest plantation, Forest managed	Rest of land use classes
Altitude (m.a.s.l.)	<450	450 - 750	750 - 2000	>2000
Slope (%)	<16	16-23	24-30	>30
Aspect (°)	-1 or 135 - 225	90 - 135 or 225 - 270	45 - 90 or 270 - 315	0 - 45 or 315 - 360
Global Tilted Irradiance, GTI (kWh/m ² /year)	>886			<886
Distance from power grid (m)	50 - 1000	1000 - 5000	5000 - 10 000	<50 or >10 000
Distance from major roads (m)	20 - 1000	1000 - 5000	>5000	<20
Distance from rivers and water surfaces (m)	100 - 1000	1000- 5000	5000 - 10 000	<100 or > 10 000
Distance from protected areas (m)	>20			<20

2.3.2 Agrovoltatics

The suitability map associated with the LAMS Agrovoltatics was created in a similar way as the map for Photovoltaic plants. Precipitation, evapotranspiration, plant available water content (PAWC) and crop types were included in this map, as well as railroads, which was merged with the roads layer. The flowchart for creating the suitability maps is presented in Figure 5 and the suitability factors and their classification is presented in Table 6.

Figure 5. Flowchart for the suitability map of the LAMS Agrovoltatics.

Table 6. Classification of the suitability factors for the LAMS Agrovoltaics.

Suitability factor	Most suitable	Moderately suitable	Least Suitable	Not suitable
Land Use	Rainfed cropland, Irrigated cropland.		Sparsely vegetated, Grassland, Shrubland	Rest of land use classes
Altitude (m.a.s.l.)	<450	450 - 750	750 - 2000	>2000
Slope (%)	<4	4 - 9	9 - 15	>15
Aspect (°)	-1 or 135 - 225	90 - 135 or 225 - 270	45 - 90 or 270 - 315	0 - 45 or 315 - 360
Global Tilted Irradiance, GTI (kWh/m ² /year)	>886			<886
Distance from power grid (m)	50 - 1000	1000 - 5000	5000 - 10 000	<50 or >10 000
Distance from major roads and railroads (m)	20 - 1000	1000 - 5000	>5000	<20
Crop type	Common Wheat, Durum Wheat, Barley, Rye, Oats, Maize, Triticale, Other cereals, Potatoes, Rape and turnip rape, Other fodder crops, Grassland	Other roots crops,	Other non permanent industrial crops, Sunflower, Soya, Dry pulses, vegetables and flowers	Rest of European Union Crop type Map classes
Plant Available Water Content, PAWC (%)	>40	20 - 40	10 - 20	0 - 10
Distance from water surfaces (m)	>100			<100
Distance from protected areas (m)	>20			<20
Annual precipitation (mm)	>450	350 - 450	250 - 350	<250
Annual evapotranspiration (mm)	>451	265 - 451	172 - 265	<172

2.3.3 Floating solar photovoltaic panels in water bodies

The suitability map associated with the LAMS Floating solar photovoltaic panels in water bodies used GTI, land use, bathymetry, power lines and protected areas as input. The only viable land use was water. The workflow for the creation of this suitability map is presented in Figure 6 and the suitability classification is presented in Table 7.

Figure 6. Flowchart for the suitability map of the LAMS Floating solar photovoltaic panels in water bodies.

Table 7. Classification of the suitability factors for the LAMS Floating solar photovoltaic panels in water bodies.

Suitability factor	Most suitable	Moderately suitable	Least Suitable	Not suitable
Land Use	Water			Rest of land use classes
Distance from protected areas (m)	>20			<20
Distance from power grid (m)	50 - 1000	1000 - 5000	5000 - 10 000	<50 or >10 000
Global Tilted Irradiance, GTI (kWh/m ² /year)	>886			<886
Water depth (m)	2 - 20			<2 or >20

2.3.4 Spatial planning for the sustainable deployment of solar energy on land

The suitability map associated with the LAMS Spatial planning for the sustainable deployment of solar energy on land has the most suitability factors. Along with the suitability factors for PV plants it included distance from forest and cropland, which were derived from the land use data. It included distance from vineyards and other tree plantations, to coast, and to religious, touristic, historical and archaeological sites. The religious, touristic, historical and archaeological site suitability factors were created in a different way than what is described in the general workflow in Figure 3. Since they consisted of both polygon, line and point layers, buffers were created for each input layer and then merged to create the suitability factor raster. Figure 7 shows workflow for the creation of this suitability map and Table 8 shows the classification of the suitability factors.

Figure 7. Flowchart for the suitability map of the LAMS Spatial planning for the sustainable deployment of solar energy on land.

Table 8. Classification of the suitability factors for the LAMS Spatial planning for the sustainable deployment of solar energy on land.

Suitability factor	Most suitable	Moderately suitable	Least Suitable	Not suitable
Land Use	Sparsely vegetated	Grassland, Shrubland		Rest of land use classes
Altitude (m.a.s.l.)	<450	450-750	750-2000	>2000
Slope (%)	<16	16-23	24-30	>30
Aspect (°)	-1 or 135 – 225	90 - 135 or 225 - 270	45 - 90 or 270 - 315	0 - 45 or 315 - 360
Distance from protected areas (m)	>20			<20
Distance from rivers (m)	>100			<100
Distance from water surfaces (m)	>50			<50
Distance from major roads (m)	20 - 1000	1000 - 5000	>5000	<20
Distance from power grid (m)	50 - 1000	1000 - 5000	5000 - 10 000	<50 or >10 000
Global Tilted Irradiance, GTI (kWh/m ² /year)	>886			<886
Distance from cropland (m)	>100			<100
Distance from forest (m)	>25			<25
Distance from vineyards and other tree plantations (m)	>25			<25
Distance from religious sites (m)	>100			<100
Distance from historical and archaeological sites (m)	>1000			<1000
Distance from touristic zones (m)	>500			<500
Distance from coastline (m)	>1000			<1000

2.3.5 Land management of solar photovoltaic systems land

There were only two suitability factors for the LAMS Land management of solar photovoltaic systems land. These were current land use and historic land use. Since this LAMS only applies to land with solar power, the only suitable class of current land use was solar land. No land in CS1 was classified as solar land and therefore no suitability map was created for CS1. Since only one suitability factor was classified using the four-grade suitability classes in this suitability map, an average calculation was not needed. This enabled a simplified approach compared to the general workflow, in which current land use was only used as a mask for historic land use. Instead of reclassifying unsuitable areas as NODATA, they were reclassified as 0. This reclassification is shown in Table 9. The layers were then multiplied to create the suitability map. Figure 8 shows the flowchart for the creation of these suitability maps and the classification of the suitability factors is presented in Table 10.

Table 9. The table shows how the suitability factors of the LAMS Land management of solar photovoltaic systems land was reclassified.

Suitability factors	Suitability classes
Historic land use	3 – Most suitable
	2 – Moderately suitable
	1 – Least suitable
	0 – Not suitable
Current land use	1 - Suitable
	0 – Not suitable

Figure 8. Flowchart for the suitability map of the LAMS Land management of solar photovoltaic systems land.

Table 10. Classification of the suitability factors for the LAMS Land management of solar photovoltaic systems land.

Suitability factor	Most suitable	Moderately suitable	Least Suitable	Not suitable
Current Land Use	Solar land			Rest of land use classes
Historic Land use	Scrub and/or herbaceous vegetation associations, Grassland and pastures	Irrigated land, Other agricultural areas	Forest, Rice field	Rest of land use classes

2.4 Data used in suitability map production

The datasets used in the creation of the suitability maps are presented in Table 11. Which OpenStreetMap (OSM) data that were used is presented in a separate table (Table 12). All data are freely available for research purposes, provided the terms of use of each dataset are followed, except for the internally produced data which are not yet available for the public at the time of writing. Most of the datasets are the same for each CS. For powerlines, an exception was made as OSM's data for powerlines in CS1 were insufficient. Data from Lantmäteriet was used instead.

The datasets for land use, plant available water content (PAWC), annual precipitation and annual evapotranspiration were produced in earlier RethinkAction work packages, before the start of this master's thesis. The land use map, called High Resolution Land Use Level 2 (HR LU L2) was created with supervised classification of multi-temporal Sentinel-2 images from 2021 and 2022 (Pérez et al. 2023). PAWC was calculated by aggregating available water content from different soil depths. The data used for this was 'SoilGrids250m - Derived available soil water capacity' by International Soil Reference and Information Centre (Sismanidis et al., 2023). The annual temperature and evapotranspiration raster data were produced together with other climate data under the name Essential Climate Variable. The data stem from eight Coupled Model Intercomparison Project Phase 6 (CMIP6) models (ibid.). The data from these models have been downscaled to each case study area. Evapotranspiration was calculated from

near surface air temperature, daily maximum near surface air temperature and daily minimum near surface air temperature (Reder et al., 2023).

Table 11. Datasets used in the creation of the suitability maps.

Dataset	Producer	Use	Data type, spatial resolution
High Resolution Land Use Level 2 (HR LU L2)	Internally produced	Land use, Distance from land use classes	Raster, 10m
ASTER Global Digital Elevation Model V003	NASA/METI/AIST /Japan Spacesystems and U.S./Japan ASTER Science Team	Elevation, Slope, Aspect	Raster, 1 arcsec
OpenStreetMap	OpenStreetMap	Roads, Railroads, Power grid, Religious sites, Touristic sites, Historical sites, Archaeological sites,	Vector
Longterm yearly average of global irradiation at optimum tilt – Global Solar Atlas 2.0	Global Solar Atlas	GTI	Raster, 9 arcsec
Rivers of Europe	Aquastat (FAO)	Rivers	Vector
Common Database on Designated Areas (CDDA)	European Environment Agency	Protected areas	Vector
European Union Crop type Map 2022	European Commission, Joint Research Centre	Crop type	Raster, 10m
Essential Climate Variable	Internally produced	Precipitation, Evapotranspiration	Raster, 2590m
Plant Available Water Content (PAWC)	Internally produced	PAWC	Raster, 250m
GLOBathy global lakes bathymetry dataset	Bahram et al.	Water depth	Raster, 30m
CORINE Land Cover 2018 (vector/raster 100 m), Europe, 6-yearly	Copernicus	Distance from certain land classes, Historic land cover	Raster, 100m
Topografi 250 Nedladdning, vektor	Lantmäteriet	Power grid for CS1	Vector

Table 12. The table shows which OSM categories were used in the suitability map production.

Factor	OSM category
Major roads	highway = motorway, trunk, primary, primary_link, secondary, secondary_link, tertiary, tertiary_link or unclassified
Power grid	power = line, minor_line or cable
Railroads	railroads
Historical and archaeological sites	archaeological_site and historic
Touristic zones	tourism
religious sites	amenity = place_of_worship

2.5 Model test with changed land data

RethinkAction focuses on land-use based solutions and the internally produced land use dataset HR LU L2 is used in the creation of multiple suitability factors. Because land use is central to the project and plays a crucial role in many of the models, changing the input data for the land use suitability factor was chosen as a means of testing the sensitivity of the models.

National Land Cover Database (NMD) by the Swedish Environmental Protection Agency was chosen for this analysis as it has classes that are easily translatable from the HR LU L2, and it has equally fine spatial resolution. NMD is a Swedish 10m resolution land cover dataset covering CS1. The dataset contains land cover and not land use but was still considered the most appropriate as the two are interchangeable for most of the suitability factors.

The GIS-models for the LAMS Photovoltaic plant, Agrovoltatics, Floating solar photovoltaic panels in water bodies, and Spatial planning for the sustainable deployment of solar energy on land, covering CS1, were run again with NMD as input data instead of HR LU L2. This affected the suitability factors for land use and other suitability factors derived for land use, such as distance from cropland, water, and forest. Table 13 shows the suitability classification of the suitability maps using NMD that were affected by the change. The GIS-model for Land management of solar photovoltaic systems land was not run again as no land was classified as solar land in CS1.

In addition to changing HR LU L2 classes into corresponding NMD classes, some additional measures had to be taken. As the NMD is a land cover dataset, it does not divide forests into primary, managed and plantation. This posed a problem for the PV plant model because it classified primary forest as unsuitable while managed and plantation forest was classified as least suitable. To account for this a mask was created from HR LU L2 containing the class Forest primary. This mask was used to exclude primary forests from the suitable areas of the NMD PV plant map.

As the NMD included land cover outside the study area, the Marine water class was used instead of the CS boundary as distance from coast. The NMD class Inland water included rivers that were used instead of the river dataset. The original map for the LAMS Spatial planning for the sustainable deployment of solar energy on land had different suitability classes for distance from rivers (100m) and distance from water (50m). As these two factors were combined in the NMD class Inland water, an average of 75m was used for both.

Table 13. Updated suitability factors for the suitability maps using NMD data. The suitability of the original factors is shown in parentheses.

LAMS	Suitability factor	Most suitable	Moderately suitable	Least suitable	Not suitable
Photovoltaic plants	Land use	Non-vegetated other open land (Sparsely vegetated)	Arable land, Vegetated other open land (Rainfed cropland, Grassland, Shrubland, Irrigated cropland)	All forest types not on wetland (Forest plantation, Forest managed)	Rest of land use classes
	Distance from rivers and water surfaces	100 – 1000 m from Inland water and Marine water	1000- 5000 m from Inland water and Marine water	5000 - 10 000 m from Inland water and Marine water	< 100 or > 10 000 m from Inland water and Marine water
Agrovoltatics	Land use	Arable land (Rainfed cropland, Irrigated cropland)		Non-vegetated other open land, Vegetated other open land (Sparsely vegetated, Grassland, Shrubland)	Rest of land use classes
	Distance from water surfaces	> 100 m from Inland water and Marine water			< 100 m from Inland water and Marine water
Floating solar photovoltaic panels in water bodies	Land use	Inland water (Water)			Rest of land use classes
Spatial planning for the sustainable deployment of solar energy on land	Land use	Non-vegetated other open land (Sparsely vegetated)	Vegetated other open land (Grassland, Shrubland)		Rest of land use classes
	Distance from rivers and	> 75 m from Inland water (> 50 m from waterbodies,			> 75 m from Inland water (< 50 m from waterbodies,

LAMS	Suitability factor	Most suitable	Moderately suitable	Least suitable	Not suitable
	water surfaces	> 100 m from rivers)			< 100 m from rivers)
	Distance from cropland	> 100 m from Arable land (> 100 m from Rainfed cropland and Irrigated cropland)			< 100 m from Arable land (< 100 m from Rainfed cropland and Irrigated cropland)
	Distance from forest	> 25 m from all forest classes			< 25 m from all forest classes

2.6 Use of GPT to collect and process data

ChatGPT 3.5 has been used to produce and correct code in the languages Python, Overpass QL and JavaScript.

Overpass QL is the language of Overpass API, which was used for downloading data from OpenStreetMap for power lines and historical, archaeological, religious, and touristic sites. The download script for the different datasets was originally produced with the “Wizard” function at Overpass Turbo (overpass-turbo.eu). ChatGPT was used as help when modifying the wizard code to meet the specific requirements of this project.

JavaScript was used to download bathymetry data via Google Earth Engine. An example script for downloading the data was provided by Google Earth Engine. This was modified to collect data within the areas of interest of this project in the correct coordinate system. ChatGPT was asked to come up with suggestions on how to modify the example code.

Python was the most extensively used programming language in this degree project. It was used to process European Union Crop type Map and OpenStreetMap data. The Python processing included clipping, reprojecting, and converting data from GeoJSON to shape files. ChatGPT was used to come with suggestions on code, to interpret error messages and to find faults in written code.

ChatGPT did not produce entire functioning scripts, though it played an important part as a faster and more precise alternative to normal search engines and programming forums.

3 Results

The result section of this thesis is divided into two main sections. The first one contains results from the RethinkAction suitability maps. The second section contains results from the model test with altered land data, as well as a comparison between these results and those of the original suitability maps.

3.1 LAMS suitability

3.1.1 Photovoltaic plants

Between 52% to 60% of the case study areas are deemed suitable for PV plant installation, with the least suitable area in CS1 (Figure 10). Almost none of the CS areas is classified as least suitable. CS2 has a larger part classified as most suitable (28%) than CS1 (4%) and CS3 (11%). By visually comparing the suitability maps we can see there are more visible continuously unsuitable areas in CS1 and CS3 than in CS2 (Figure 9).

Figure 9. Suitability map for the LAMS Photovoltaic plants for CS1, 2 and 3.

Figure 10. Percentual distribution of suitability classes for the LAMS Photovoltaic plants in CS1, 2 and 3.

Looking at the amount of area that each suitability factor classifies as not suitable, we can see that aspect is the top constricting factor for all case studies (Table 14). For CS1 the factors land use, protected areas and distance from power lines classified more than 10% of the CS as not suitable. The second most constricting factor for CS2 was distance from roads (9%) and for CS3 it was protected areas (7%). There is a noteworthy difference in how large part of each CS that is classified as not suitable because of protected areas.

Table 14. Percentage of area classified as not suitable for each factor of the LAMS Photovoltaic plants.

Suitability factor	CS1	CS2	CS3
Aspect	23%	24%	24%
Land use	15%	4%	6%
Protected areas	13%	1%	7%
Dist. to power lines	11%	3%	4%
Dist. to water	5%	6%	4%
Dist. to roads	4%	9%	2%
Slope	1%	5%	2%
Altitude	0%	0%	0%
GTI	0%	0%	0%

Of the area classified as suitable for PV plants in all factors, the distribution of suitability per factor is shown in Table 15. Notable details in the table are that CS2 has a larger part most suitable areas in the factors distance from roads and distance from water than the other two case studies. Aspect and altitude are almost identical between the case studies.

Table 15. Distribution of the suitability of each four-grade suitability factor, for the pixels classified as suitable for PV plants.

Suitability	CS1			CS2			CS3		
	1	2	3	1	2	3	1	2	3
Roads	0%	11%	89%	0%	1%	99%	0%	43%	57%
Water	0%	63%	37%	1%	31%	68%	4%	66%	30%
Land use	51%	49%	0%	24%	76%	0%	13%	87%	0%
Power lines	25%	56%	19%	10%	55%	35%	1%	49%	50%
Slope	2%	8%	91%	6%	14%	80%	3%	9%	88%
Aspect	33%	33%	35%	33%	32%	35%	32%	32%	35%
Altitude	0%	0%	100%	0%	0%	100%	0%	0%	100%

3.1.2 Agrovoltatics

There are less suitable areas for agrovoltatics than for PV plants (Figure 11 and 12). CS3 has perceptually most suitable areas, 20% moderately suitable and 21% most suitable, followed by CS2. The same patches of unsuitable land that were seen in the PV plant maps are visible in the Agrovoltatics map.

Figure 11. Suitability map for the LAMS Agrovoltatics for CS1, 2 and 3.

Figure 12. Percentual distribution of suitability classes for the LAMS Agrovoltatics in CS1, 2 and 3.

Crop type and land use are the most constricting factors for agrovoltatics suitability (Table 16). These factors are heavily overlapping as all land use other than cropland will not have a crop type and will therefore not be suitable. There is a relatively large difference in how constricting these factors are, where CS1 has the least areas with suitable crop type (44%) and land use (40%) and CS3 has the most, with 71% of the study area with suitable crop type and 82% with suitable land use.

Table 16. Percentage of area classified as not suitable for each factor of the LAMS Agrovoltaics.

Suitability factor	CS1	CS2	CS3
Crop type	66%	45%	25%
Land use	60%	29%	18%
Aspect	23%	24%	24%
Slope	12%	26%	15%
Protected areas	13%	1%	7%
Power lines	11%	3%	4%
Roads	4%	9%	2%
Water	5%	5%	3%
PAWC	3%	2%	4%
Altitude	0%	0%	0%
Evapotranspiration	0%	0%	0%
Precipitation	0%	0%	0%
GTI	0%	0%	0%

Regarding the areas classified as suitable for agrovoltaics, we can see a large difference in how PAWC and distance from roads affects the suitability differently in the case studies (Table 17). CS2 has a higher percentage of areas with moderately suitable PAWC than the other case studies. CS1 and CS2 have more areas with most suitable distance from roads than CS3.

Table 17. Distribution of the suitability of each four-grade suitability factor, for the pixels classified as suitable for Agrovoltaics.

Suitability	CS1			CS2			CS3		
	1	2	3	1	2	3	1	2	3
PAWC	92%	8%	0%	0%	100%	0%	41%	59%	0%
Roads	0%	6%	94%	0%	0%	100%	0%	40%	60%
Power lines	22%	60%	19%	9%	55%	36%	1%	47%	52%
Land use	14%	0%	86%	0%	0%	100%	1%	0%	99%
Crop type	4%	0%	96%	19%	0%	81%	11%	0%	89%
Slope	26%	46%	29%	33%	44%	23%	30%	46%	24%
Aspect	32%	32%	35%	34%	32%	34%	32%	32%	36%
Altitude	0%	0%	100%	0%	0%	100%	0%	0%	100%
Precipitation	0%	0%	100%	0%	0%	100%	0%	0%	100%
Evapo- transpiration	0%	0%	100%	0%	0%	100%	0%	0%	100%

3.1.3 Floating solar photovoltaic panels in water bodies

Figure 13 shows where the water in the case studies is situated and which part of those areas are suitable for FPV. Between 6 and 12% of the water areas in the case studies are classified as suitable for FPV (Figure 14). It is worth noting that these water areas do not only contain still waterbodies, but also larger rivers. For CS1 some water pixels are outside the coast of Gotland, as the case study boundary file did not precisely follow the

coastline. Between 0.06% and 0.17% of the total case study areas are suitable for FPV (Table 18).

Figure 13. Suitability map for the LAMS Floating solar photovoltaic panels in water bodies for CS1, 2 and 3. The unsuitable areas are divided into not suitable water and not suitable land.

Figure 14. Percentual distribution of suitability classes of all land classified as water for the LAMS Floating solar photovoltaic panels in water bodies in CS1, 2 and 3.

Table 18. The table shows the amount of suitable area for the LAMS Floating solar photovoltaic panels in water bodies in percentage of the total area for each CS.

	CS1	CS2	CS3
Unsuitable area	99.83%	99.93%	99.94%
Suitable area	0.17%	0.07%	0.06%

Of the areas with land use classified as water, Table 19 shows how large part that is considered not suitable for each factor. The dataset used for water depth did not cover all the areas classified as water in the land use dataset. This is partly because the water depth dataset only covers lakes while the land use dataset included large rivers and seawater, but it could also be partly because of misclassification or differences in minimal mapping unit between the datasets. Between 59 and 91% of the land use water

areas were not included in the water depth dataset. Of the remaining areas, 11% of CS1, 7% of CS3 and only 1% of CS2 had too shallow or deep water. 19% of the water areas were either too close or too far away from power lines in CS1, compared to only 2% for CS2 and 1% for CS3. Distance from power lines was the only factor that affected the suitability gradient of the suitability maps as the other factors only classified areas as suitable or not suitable.

Table 19. Percentage of water classified as not suitable in each suitability factor. The suitability factor Water depth is divided into areas classified as not suitable because of the actual water depth, and areas classified as not suitable because of data unavailability in the dataset.

Suitability factor	CS1	CS2	CS3
Water depth (no data)	59%	91%	79%
Water depth (not suitable)	11%	1%	7%
Protected areas	33%	28%	32%
Power lines	19%	2%	1%
GTI	0%	0%	0%

3.1.4 Spatial planning for the sustainable deployment of solar energy on land

There are very few areas classified as suitable for Spatial planning for the sustainable deployment of solar energy on land. CS1 has the largest part suitable areas, 0.5% (Figure 16). Patches of suitable land is visible for CS1 but for CS2 and CS3 it is not visible unless zoomed in (Figure 15).

Figure 15. Suitability map for the LAMS Spatial planning for the sustainable deployment of solar energy on land for CS1, 2 and 3.

Figure 16. Percentual distribution of suitability classes for the LAMS Spatial planning for the sustainable deployment of solar energy on land in CS1, 2 and 3.

Land use is the by far the most constricting factor for this LAMS in all study areas (Table 20). Only 12% of CS1 has land use considered suitable of this LAMS. For CS3 that figure is 1% and for CS2 only 0.1%. Together with the factors distance to cropland and distance from forest almost all areas are considered not suitable. On top of this there are 14 other suitability factors, each classifying between 0-24% of the case studies as not suitable.

Table 20. Percentage of area classified as not suitable for each factor of the LAMS Spatial planning for the sustainable deployment of solar energy on land.

Suitability Factor	CS1	CS2	CS3
Land use	88%	99.9%	99%
Distance from cropland	51%	95%	94%
Distance from forest	64%	35%	17%
Aspect	23%	24%	24%
Historical / Archaeological site	12%	25%	14%
Protected area	13%	1%	7%
Power line	11%	3%	4%
Coast	16%	0%	0%
Touristic zone	5%	6%	4%
Roads	4%	9%	2%
Water	2%	3%	2%
Slope	1%	5%	2%
Vineyard and other tree plantation	0%	4%	3%
River	0%	2%	2%
Religious site	0%	0%	0%
Altitude	0%	0%	0%
GTI	0%	0%	0%

3.1.5 Land management of solar photovoltaic systems land

The LAMS Land management of solar photovoltaic systems land only analyses land classified as solar land. Since no areas was classified as solar land in CS1, no areas are suitable there and therefore no suitability map was created. The solar land area in CS2 and 3 are quite few and is only visible when zooming in on the maps (Figure 17).

Previous land use is the only factor classifying the solar land suitability for land management. CS2 and 3 have similar distribution of suitability, with CS3 having somewhat more suitable land (Figure 18).

Figure 17. Suitability map for the LAMS Land management of solar photovoltaic systems land for CS1, 2 and 3. The unsuitable areas are divided into not suitable solar land and not suitable other land.

Figure 18. Percentual distribution of suitability classes of land classified as solar land for the LAMS Land management of solar photovoltaic systems land in CS2 and 3.

3.2 Model test with changed land data

Changing the land data, from the internally produced HR LU L2 to the Swedish Environmental Protection Agency’s land cover dataset NMD, affects the LAMS Floating solar photovoltaic panels in water bodies the least (Table 21). This is because the only land cover considered in this suitability map is whether it is water or not. 9% of suitable pixels for PV plants and 10% of the suitable pixels Agrovoltatics are changed in some way when switching the land data. For the LAMS Spatial planning for the sustainable deployment of solar energy on land, 62% of the suitable pixels are changed.

Table 21. The table show the percentage of pixels changed per suitability class when switching the HR LU L2 dataset to NMD. The table also shows the total percentage of pixels changed and the percentage of suitable pixels changed. Changes <5% is shown as light green, 5-20% is shown as dark green, 20-50% is shown as yellow and >50% is shown as red.

Percentage of pixels changed	PV	AV	FPV	SP
Not suitable	2%	0.5%	0.0001%	0.7%
Least suitable	25%	0%	0.4%	37%
Moderately suitable	8%	9%	0.1%	61%
Most suitable	13%	10%	0.06%	65%
Total	5%	2%	0.0003%	1%
Total suitable	9%	10%	0.2%	62%

3.2.1 Photovoltaic plants

5% of pixels in the PV plants suitability map was changed when switching land data (Table 21). Of these changed pixels 45% were changed from one suitable class to another. 40% of the changed pixels were changed from suitable to not suitable and 16% from not suitable to suitable (Figure 19b).

The distribution of suitable land for photovoltaic plants is fairly similar between the maps using HR LU L2 data and NMD data. The map using NMD has 1.2 percentage points less suitable pixels in total but 1.7 percentage points more most suitable pixels (Figure 19a).

Figure 19. The figure shows how changing the land data affects the distribution of the suitability for PV plants. Part a) shows a comparison of suitability between the map made with HR LU L2 data and NMD data. Part b) shows how the altered pixels were redistributed when switching land use data.

3.2.2 Agrovoltatics

Only 2% of the pixels changed suitability class in the agrovoltatics map when switching land data (Table 21). 25% of the changed pixels were changed between suitable classes, 57% were changed to suitable pixels and 17% were changed to non-suitable pixels (Figure 20b). This has almost no effect on the total distribution of suitability in percentage. Rounded to integers the distribution is exactly the same between the suitability map using HR LU L2 data and the one using NMD data (Figure 20a).

Figure 20. The figure shows how changing the land data affects the distribution of the suitability for Agrovoltatics. Part a) shows a comparison of suitability between the map made with HR LU L2 data and NMD data. Part b) shows how the altered pixels were redistributed when switching land use data.

3.2.3 Spatial planning for the sustainable deployment of solar energy on land

Only 2% of the pixels in the suitability map for Spatial planning for the sustainable deployment of solar energy on land changed suitability when switching land dataset (Table 21). This is mainly a consequence of the fact that almost all area is classified as not suitable in both the suitability map created with HR LU L2 and the one created with NMD data. Of the pixels classified as suitable in the suitability map created with HR LU L2, 62% are changed. Almost no pixels are changed between different suitable classes (Figure 21b). Instead, pixels are classified from suitable to not suitable and vice versa. 49% of the pixels changed from suitable to not suitable were changed due to differences in land classification of the specific pixel. The other 51% were reclassified to not suitable because of their distance from cropland or forest pixels.

The suitability map created with NMD classifies almost twice as many pixels as suitable compared to the one created with HR LU L2, 0.9% compared to 0.5% (Figure 21a).

Figure 21. The figure shows how changing the land data affects the distribution of suitability of the suitability for Spatial planning for the sustainable deployment of solar energy on land. Part a) shows a comparison of suitability between the map made with HR LU L2 data and NMD data. Part b) shows how the altered pixels were redistributed when switching land use data.

4 Discussion

4.1 Case study suitability for the different LAMS

The results shows that CS1, Gotland, has the smallest percentage of area suitable for PV plants. This is explained by less suitable land use, a higher percentage of protected areas and a less extended power grid. CS1 has less percentual area suitable for agrovoltatics as well, which is largely explained by the same factors. CS1 has less land use classified as rainfed or irrigated cropland (29%, compared to 71% of CS2 and 80% of CS3) and more

primary forest (10%, compared to 0% of CS2 and 1% of CS3). This heavily constricts the potential for photovoltaic plants and agrovoltaics in CS1, compared to the other case studies. CS3, Southern Great Plain, has a larger part suitable areas for both PV plants and agrovoltaics than CS2, though CS2 has a larger part classified as most suitable for PV plants. The proximity to roads and water is largely contributing to the higher suitability classification of PV plants in CS2.

As for FPV, CS1 has a somewhat larger percentage of water surfaces classified as suitable than the other study areas. This is mainly because of the data availability of the water depth dataset. This could be due to that the HR LU L2 water surfaces are partly rivers and oceans or other water areas not suitable for FPV installation, but it could also be caused by misclassification or lack of data. Therefore, no conclusions are drawn from this comparison. When comparing the suitable area of FPV with the total area of the case studies, CS1 still has the largest area classified as suitable. However, the uncertainty arising from the lack of overlap between the water depth and land use data is still preventing conclusive conclusions. The results from the FPV can still be used as a suggestion of suitable areas for FPV installation, but it is important to note that there may be other suitable areas within case studies that were excluded because of data unavailability.

CS1 has the largest percentual area classified as suitable for spatial planning for the sustainable deployment of solar energy on land. CS1 has more grasslands and less cropland than CS2 and CS3 which makes it somewhat more suitable, but because of the requirements of LAMS in terms of numerous factors with strict suitability classification values, only 0.5% of the total area of CS1 is classified as suitable.

Most areas in CS2 and CS3 currently containing PV plants are classified as suitable for some sort of land management. This report does not go into greater detail of what type of land management that could be, as this suitability map mostly serves as an input for further analysis in the RethinkAction project.

The suitability maps produced in this project can serve as a basis for spatial planning of solar power solutions in the case study areas. The suitability map for PV plants suggests large areas suitable for PV installation. As some of the land suggested in this map is situated on cropland, the use of only this map can lead to conflicts of aim between food production and renewable energy production. To avoid this land use conflict the suitability maps for agrovoltaics, FPV and spatial planning for the sustainable deployment of solar energy on land can be used. The LAMS with most potential land among these is agrovoltaics, with between 19% and 41% of the regions classified as suitable in the case studies, and between 6% and 21% classified as most suitable.

4.2 Possibilities and limitations of the method

This degree project presents detailed instructions for creating suitability maps for different types of solar power solutions, as well as a general instruction which can be adapted for other types of suitability maps. The possibilities of the method presented in this degree project are associated with the wide-ranging conditions it was created for. In contrast to previous similar studies (e.g. Elkadeem et al., 2024; Günen 2021; Noorollahi et al., 2016; Spyridonidou et al., 2022) that focuses on a single region or country, the method in this degree was developed to fit a wide range of land characteristics. By using six European case studies, chosen based of their diverse characteristics, the method presented above is adapted to fit the whole European continent. The models built in this project uses data that are freely available for research purposes, on European and global level. The models and method described in this paper can therefore be used for similar studies of other areas in Europe, and with some adjustments it can be outside of Europe as well. The general applicability of this method comes with lack of precision. A method

developed for a specific area can yield more precise results if adapted correctly for the specific attributes of that area.

According to Spyridonidou et al. (2022), issues that can affect the results of a PV suitability map can stem from data inaccuracy, choice of suitability factors and how the factors are weighted against each other. In the method on this degree project, averaging was used as a way of combining the suitability factors into one suitability map. The outcome of this approach is that all factors have an equally large impact on the final suitability classification. In many other similar studies, a weighted overlay is used, where the suitability factors are given different weights based on expert opinion of the importance of the factor (e.g. Elkadeem et al., 2024; Günen 2021; Noorollahi et al., 2016; Spyridonidou et al., 2022). It was not possible to gather such expert opinion during the scope of this thesis, but to further develop this method a weighted overlay is recommended.

As for the data, the models used to create the suitability maps rely on data from OSM for roads, power grid, railroads, and touristic, religious, historical, and archaeological sites. OSM is an example on volunteered geographic information, where the data production and editing are crowd-sourced (Mooney & Minghini, 2017). This is a potential source of error as there is no guarantee of data quality. The different data editors might have use different tags for the data which is to consider a potential flaw as the selection of OSM-data is solemnly based on these tags. A further exploration of the object included in the downloaded OSM data would have yielded more reliable results, though it would have taken a considerable amount of time as these datasets included a great number of objects that are not always well structured.

The FPV suitability map was constricted by the waterbodies included in the water depth dataset. A water depth dataset which included more waterbodies might have resulted in more suitable FPV areas. The difference in coverage between the water depth dataset and the water in the land use dataset was discovered late in the process and could therefore not be exchanged to different data.

4.3 Output comparison of suitability maps using different land data

As described in the section 2.4, the land use data were considered as an important factor to test regarding potential issues of data inaccuracy. After exchanging the land dataset, the differences were minimal for the FPV and agrovoltatics suitability, and some changes could be seen for the PV suitability. The largest effect of this land use dataset change was seen in the suitability map for Spatial planning for the sustainable deployment of solar energy on land, where 62% of the suitable pixels were classified as not suitable after changing the land use data. About half of the pixels were changed because of their distance from cropland or forests and not because of the land use of the reclassified pixel. The land use in this LAMS has a larger effect on the outcome as it does not only use land use as a suitability factor by itself, but also used distance from cropland and forests as factors based on the land use data. Each pixel classified as cropland affects the suitability of a 100m radius and each forest pixel affects a 25m radius. For continuous patches of cropland or forest the effect of misclassification is small, but if secluded patches would be misclassified as cropland or forest it would have a larger effect on the output suitability map. A way to avoid this risk would be using distance from clusters of cropland or forest as a suitability factor instead of distance from each single cropland or forest pixel.

5 Conclusions

This degree project presents a methodology for assessing suitability of solar power solution, adapted to suit the different land characteristics of the European continent. The suitability maps created show that Southern Great Plain in Hungary has the most potential area for photovoltaic plants and agrovoltatics of the analysed study areas. Tarn-et-Garonne in France has the second largest share of suitable areas, but for photovoltaic plants it has the largest share of highly suitable areas. Gotland in Sweden has the least suitable areas for both photovoltaic plants and agrovoltatics. The differences between the case studies are associated with the differences in land use, where Southern Great Plain and Tarn-et-Garonne have a larger percentage of cropland and a smaller percentage of forested areas. If a stricter suitability classification is implemented, where cropland is not deemed suitable for PV installation, Gotland has the largest percentual area suitable. To further develop this methodology a weighted overlay, based on expert opinion, could be implemented to give more important factors a larger impact on the suitability map. Furthermore, a more thorough examination of the input data would be beneficial to avoid areas being classified as unsuitable because of data unavailability or data misclassification.

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